

Effect of Wrinkling Allowance in Tensile Membrane Structures

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Abstract

Wrinkling is a common phenomenon in tensile membrane structures (TMS), which are widely used in architectural applications because they are lightweight, flexible, and have an aesthetic appeal. However, wrinkling can affect the stress distribution and overall performance of TMS. Current practices and literature aim to completely prevent wrinkling by ensuring that the membrane remains under tensile stress (in all directions) throughout its service life. Achieving this “no wrinkling” state often requires prestressing the fabric to higher levels, thereby increasing the stress even before any external loads are applied. Therefore, this action has a potential to reduce the external load carrying capacity against tearing failure. On the other hand, allowing excessive wrinkling may compromise the aesthetics of the structure, although the presence of wrinkles does not necessarily indicate structural damage. Therefore, allowing a controlled amount of wrinkling can help prevent membrane stresses from exceeding permissible limits under load, while maintaining aesthetic and functional integrity. This paper investigates the impact of tolerating some degree of wrinkling on the limit state of tearing of tensile membranes. The objective is to develop a deeper understanding of the relationship between the spread of wrinkles and the stress thresholds, providing insights that can inform design strategies and ensure structural integrity. Case studies are presented, covering both fundamental and complex TMS shapes under various load cases.

Keywords: tensile membrane structures, tensile fabrics, membrane wrinkling, limit state, design code development

1. Introduction

Tensile membrane structures (TMS), such as fabric canopies and architectural membranes, efficiently use materials to cover large spans with minimal support. Since the bending or compressive rigidity of membranes are negligible, they rely on prestress to maintain their shape and resist external loads, such as wind, snow, or rain. However, these structures also present various unique challenges, including particularly the tendency for wrinkling under compression. Wrinkling in a membrane occurs when folds, creases, or ripples form on its surface due to insufficient tensile stress in the membrane. This happens when adequate pretension have not been applied on the membrane to keep it stretched or when tension acts unevenly, creating regions of high and low stress, sometimes exceeding expected levels under external loading. Fig. 1 shows a tensile membrane structure—typical in its usage as a roof over an open walkway or platform—and how parts of this membrane has formed wrinkles.

Wrinkling can affect a membrane’s appearance, performance, and even structural integrity, potentially compromising its effectiveness and usability. To prevent or minimize wrinkling, a proper design, adequate pretensioning, and sufficient supports are essential. Recent advancements have enabled the quantification of wrinkles using methods such as digital image correction [3] and analytical models based on piecewise stress fields [4] or the maximization of tensile strain energy [5]. However, treatment of membrane wrinkling in the design process is far from being standardized. The few standards and guidelines that are available on TMS worldwide do not

Figure 1: (a) TMS outside Mumbai airport, India [1], and (b) closer view showing wrinkles formed in the membrane [2].

adequately specify wrinkling mitigating design steps, and stop at mentioning that wrinkling should be kept at a minimum and is project dependent.

This paper focuses on the concept of wrinkling allowance, which is a *design consideration* that allows controlled wrinkling within acceptable limits to prevent localized stress concentrations. This is an alternative to wrinkling prevention. The main objective of this paper is to examine how different levels of wrinkling affect the membrane's ability to maintain stresses within limits and prevent failure. Two “benchmark” examples are presented to evaluate the impact of wrinkling on stress behavior concerning the wrinkled area of the membrane.

2. Wrinkling in membranes

Wrinkles are localized “buckling” deformations that occur in membranes subjected to compressive stresses [6]. While tensile stresses produce predictable elastic deformations, compressive stresses lead to out-of-plane deformations due to the membrane's inability to resist them, resulting in instabilities. The initiation and propagation of wrinkles are influenced by several factors, including material properties (elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio), membrane geometry (shape, dimensions, and pre-existing imperfections from patterning), and loading conditions (magnitude, distribution, and rate of load application). Additionally, environmental factors such as temperature and humidity can alter material properties, further contributing to the possibility of wrinkling, particularly in applications exposed to significant environmental variations.

2.1. Modeling of membrane wrinkling in TMS load analysis

The analysis of TMS under applied loads, such as wind and snow, follows the methodology described in [7]. Here, membrane wrinkling is assessed using a mixed stress-strain criterion based on [8]. Under applied loads, if the minimum principal stress in the membrane is positive ($\sigma_{\min} > 0$), the membrane is in a ‘taut’ state, indicating a fully tensioned state. If the minimum principal stress is negative and the maximum strain is positive ($\sigma_{\min} \leq 0$ and $\epsilon_{\max} > 0$), the membrane enters a ‘wrinkled’ state, where localized compressive stresses cause wrinkling. Additionally, if the maximum membrane strain is non-positive ($\epsilon_{\max} \leq 0$), the membrane is in a ‘slack’ state, signifying a completely loose state with no tensile forces.

The load analysis is performed by minimizing the potential energy of the TMS. To incorporate this wrinkling model into the analysis of the form-found configuration of the TMS, a modified membrane potential energy ($\tilde{\pi}_M$) is defined by modifying the stress and strain tensors:

$$\tilde{\pi}_M = \int \frac{1}{2} \{\mathbf{E}'\}^T \mathbf{C} \{\mathbf{E}'\} + \{\mathbf{S}^0\}^T \{\mathbf{E}'\} dV \quad (1)$$

where, \mathbf{S}^0 is the initial prestress, and \mathbf{E}' denotes the piecewise modified Green-Lagrange strain, which is equal to the modified strain $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$ if wrinkled and the original strain \mathbf{E} when taut. The modified potential is zero when the element is in a slack state.

An orthotropic material constitutive tensor (\mathbf{C}) is employed, with E_1 and E_2 representing the elastic moduli in the fill and warp directions, respectively. The Poisson's ratios, ν_{12} and ν_{21} , are related by the condition $E_1\nu_{21} = E_2\nu_{12}$ and G represents the shear modulus of the membrane. The modification to the strain tensor is done using tension field theory (Eq. 2) and uniaxial tension conditions (Eq. 3), ensuring that there are no axial or shear stresses along the direction of wrinkling.

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}} = \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{2} (\eta \mathbf{V}_1 \otimes \mathbf{V}_1) \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_1 \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \cdot \mathbf{V}_1 = 0; \quad \mathbf{V}_1 \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{S}} \cdot \mathbf{V}_2 = 0 \quad (3)$$

where η and \mathbf{V}_1 represent the magnitude and direction of the wrinkles, respectively, and \mathbf{V}_2 is the direction orthogonal to the wrinkles.

2.2. Wrinkling design

Currently, most design guidelines and even the research on reducing wrinkling in membranes focus on the complete prevention of surface wrinkles. This may be due to the challenges in modeling wrinkling and the relative ease of incorporating a minimum principal stress based criterion that ensures the membrane stresses remain tensile. Some design guidelines, *eg*, [6], have however recommended the establishment of project-specific limits for wrinkling. It is also well documented that the occurrence of wrinkles does not necessarily indicate structural failure [9].

“Wrinkles do not mean damage to the membrane—unless they occur repeatedly—but for aesthetic reasons the aim should be to avoid wrinkles. However, a complete avoidance is unrealistic for most membranes. A limitation of wrinkles should be envisaged.”

Wrinkling, thus, is more of a serviceability (or aesthetics) issue than that of strength (or collapse). A small amount of wrinkling is typically allowed near the corners and edges based on the designer's experience. A project-specific limit on the percentage of the membrane area affected by wrinkles may also be established, while keeping aesthetics in consideration. This approach can be adopted thanks to the wrinkling modeling presented in Sec. 2.1., where the spreading of wrinkles on a TMS membrane surface can be quantified in the load analysis stage. This limit on the wrinkled area can also take into account the location of the wrinkles within the membrane, if needed.

3. Wrinkling allowance

As mentioned earlier, a complete prevention of wrinkling may lead to unwanted stress conditions in the membrane in terms of membrane tearing under external loads. The effect of reducing the membrane's load-carrying capacity while achieving a 'no wrinkling' condition through (increased) prestressing therefore needs to be analyzed thoroughly. The following methodology is employed in this paper towards this analysis. At first, a TMS shape is selected and the TMS is then subjected to an initial prestress, which is reasonable from a design perspective. The form-finding analysis is then carried out using the updated weight method [10]. Using the form-found shape obtained this way, a static load analysis is conducted under the action of wind or snow loads. The maximum membrane stresses and the extent of membrane wrinkling, expressed as a percentage of the total membrane area, are measured using the analysis methods described in Sec. 2.1.. The percentage wrinkled area can be described as

$$w_p = \frac{A_w}{A} \times 100; \quad A_w = \sum_i^{i \in \mathcal{W}} A_i \quad (4)$$

Figure 2: Schematic diagram showing the available design space in terms of prestress.

where w_p is the wrinkling percentage, A is the total membrane area and A_w is the total area of the wrinkled elements. \mathcal{W} is defined as

$$\mathcal{W} = \{e : e_i \in E; S_{\min}^i \leq 0; E_{\min}^i > 0\} \quad (5)$$

where, for every element e in E , the criterion for wrinkling is satisfied.

The TMS experiences stresses due to applied pretension even in the absence of any external loads. When subjected to external loads, the stress in the membrane increases. The safety of the TMS against tearing failure can be measured using the factor of safety (FoS):

$$\Omega = \frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma_{\max}} \quad (6)$$

which is the ratio of the ultimate tensile strength (σ_u) of the membrane fabric to the maximum stress (σ_{\max}) acting on the whole membrane on account of the applied loads. This factor indicates a safety margin that must account for various influences, including biaxial stress effects, environmental impacts due to aging and deterioration, varying load durations, temperature effects, and the chances of defects in larger surfaces, that are not explicitly incorporated in the stress calculations. Additionally, it should also take care of other unspecified effects and inherent uncertainties in material properties, geometry, and analysis. Consequently, a large factor of safety between 5 to 10 is typically adopted in practice [11].

In order to understand the effect of increasing the membrane prestress in order to control (or prevent) wrinkling, on the margin against tearing failure, the prestress is varied for an otherwise same design scenario. As the prestress is increased to control the spread of wrinkles on the membrane surface, the FoS correspondingly decreases. This relationship helps in the determination of the minimum wrinkle area that has to be allowed for maintaining a minimum FoS. This FoS (Ω_{\min}) and the minimum wrinkled area ($w_{p,\min}$) both correspond to the maximum applicable prestress, as shown in the schematic in Fig. 2. On the other side, for aesthetic reasons, the permissible level of wrinkling may have to be constrained to a specified maximum limit ($w_{p,\max}$), which dictates the minimum required prestress. The range between the two prestress levels is the design space available to the designer for the given design scenario.

However, achieving a very precise prestress intensity in TMS is quite challenging in practice due to several factors, including slip during prestressing, elastic shortening, creep, shrinkage, and membrane relaxation under environmental conditions. Therefore, a sufficiently flexible design space is essential for designers to accommodate these practical limitations.

4. Numerical examples

To illustrate the relationship between the wrinkling area and the safety against tearing, two TMS examples are considered as shown in Fig. 3: (a) a square conic, and (b) a twin hyper. Further details on these TMS and the

Figure 3: (a) Square conic TMS; (b) Twin hyperbolic TMS.

corresponding results are discussed in the following subsections.

4.1. Example 1: A square conic TMS

The example considered is a frame-supported conic structure, adapted from Gosling *et al.* [12]. This high-point structure has a square base measuring $14\text{ m} \times 14\text{ m}$ and a fixed circular head ring with a diameter of 5 m , positioned 4 m above the base (Fig. 3a). The membrane material is assumed to be PES/PVC fabric, with an ultimate tensile strength of 65 kN/m . The elastic modulus is taken as 600 kN/m , the shear modulus as 30 kN/m , and the Poisson's ratio as 0.4 . A uniform snow load of 0.66 kN/m^2 , acting vertically downward, is considered. The prestress in the membrane is increased from 1 kN/m to 5 kN/m , and the resulting variation in the FoS (Ω) and the wrinkled area (w_p) expressed as a percentage of the total membrane area, are presented in Fig. 4a.

Figure 4: Prestress vs. factor of safety and wrinkled area percentage for the (a) square conic TMS, and the (b) twin hyperbolic TMS.

From the plot, it is observed that achieving a wrinkle-free state requires a prestress of 4.15 kN/m . However, this results in a FoS of 4.8 , which is not acceptable according to most global design standards. Considering the minimum FoS required to be 5.0 , a minimum of 2.1% of total membrane area should be allowed to wrinkle. Correspondingly, a maximum prestress of 3.9 kN/m can be applied to keep $\Omega \geq 5.0$. Fig. 5a marks the 2.1% wrinkled area in black color, and also shows the location of wrinkling on a top view of this TMS.

It is difficult to put a maximum limit on w_p for aesthetic reasons, as it can be subjective. Let's suppose the wrinkles should be limited to a maximum of 15% in this specific case, as shown in Fig. 5b. The prestress in the membrane, correspondingly, needs to be more than 2.86 kN/m . Thus, the designer can specify a prestress between 2.86 kN/m and 3.9 kN/m balancing safety against tearing and the serviceability criterion for wrinkling.

4.2. Example 2: Twin hyperbolic

The second example involves a 'twin hyperbolic' TMS, which consists of a cable-supported structure featuring three diagonal pairs of alternating high and low points (Fig. 3b). This TMS has plan dimensions of $12\text{ m} \times 6\text{ m}$

Figure 5: Square conic TMS with (a) 2.1% area wrinkled, and (b) 15% area wrinkled (wrinkled regions are marked in black).

and a height difference of 4 m between the high and low points. The membrane material is assumed to be PTFE-coated glass fabric, with an ultimate tensile strength of 80 kN/m [9]. The elastic modulus is taken as 1400 kN/m in the warp direction and 800 kN/m in the fill direction, while the shear modulus is 100 kN/m and the Poisson's ratio is 0.8. The edge cables have a diameter of 19 mm, an elastic modulus of 205 GPa, and are prestressed to 50 kN [12]. A uniform wind uplift of intensity 1.0 kN/m², acting perpendicular to the membrane surface, is considered. The prestress in the membrane is varied from 1 kN/m to 5 kN/m, and the resulting variations in Ω and w_p are presented in Fig. 4b.

Figure 6: Twin hyperbolic TMS with (a) 0.06% area wrinkled, and (b) 5% area wrinkled (wrinkled regions are marked in black).

A slight allowance for wrinkling (0.06% or more, Fig. 6a) can achieve a FoS of 5 or higher at a prestress level of 6.55 kN/m or less. In contrast, without any wrinkling allowance, a prestress of 7.3 kN/m is required, which results in an unacceptable FoS of 4.66. If a maximum wrinkling limit of 5% is permitted (Fig. 6b), the designer has a viable prestress range between 3.12 kN/m and 6.55 kN/m, providing greater flexibility in the design process. It should be noted here that in plan view (Fig. 6), the structure is symmetric about the vertical centreline, but not symmetric about the horizontal centreline.

5. Conclusion

The stability of a TMS is achieved through prestressing, which effectively reduces chances of membrane instability through wrinkling or ponding. However, excessive prestress increases membrane stress levels, potentially compromising the load-carrying capacity and leading towards a failure by membrane tearing. The demonstration examples presented in this paper show how eliminating wrinkling completely through the application of higher prestress may lead to a reduction of the safety margin (or, factor of safety) against tearing failure below its acceptable limits. Therefore, depending on the scenario, some percentage of wrinkling is actually necessary to keep the FoS above the minimum acceptable value.

On the other hand, wrinkles affect the visual appearance of the structure and, if excessive, can compromise

structural safety. So a designer should also put a limit on the maximum allowable wrinkled area. This serviceability limit is difficult to establish since the aesthetic sense varies among designers and users. A balance must be achieved between ensuring structural safety against tearing and maintaining aesthetics by limiting wrinkles. This study highlights the importance of predicting wrinkles through appropriate analysis techniques and establishes a design space for prestress that allows both of these controls.

However, a more detailed exploration of the ideas presented here is necessary to bring this concept to an implementation stage and then to standardize. Future works in this area should consider the effects of uncertainties more thoroughly, such that specifications can be developed for a modern reliability-based design code. Also, further efforts towards “quantifying” the acceptable look of a TMS with wrinkles will be necessary in this regard.

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